

CLIMATE CHANGE: ITS EFFECT TO THE GROWTH OF PLANTS

Jennylaine S. Hadjibun, Fatima Ryza I. Bakil, Arliena A. Balli, Barie T. Hadjimulla,
Nur-Shahaana P. Hajiri, Ainul I. Bakil, Jul-asri A. Hadjibun,
Maryjoy A. Busaña, Narsima A. Sabbaha

Mindanao State University-Sulu, Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on the effects of climate change to the growth of plants. Through qualitative methods, the study provides perceptions about what way does climate change affects the living of plants. With the help of interview guided questions, the researchers gathered the data needed. The findings show that plants face a lot of challenges due to climate change, from its quality to the way it develops and grow. As well as ways on how the caretakers of a farm adapt to the changes induced by climate change, how planting dates is relevant to climate change albeit being unpredictable. By understanding the effects and factors contributing to climate change, this study contributes to gaining further knowledge on techniques, precautionary measures, and flexibility on the effect of climate change to the growth of plants; proper management, organic fertilizer, greenhouse, mulching techniques, and organic agriculture are recommended.

Keywords: *climate change, growth of plants, MSU-Sulu Philippines, qualitative, interview, factors*

INTRODUCTION

One of the issues of our day is climate change, which is increasingly evident. It is becoming more and more obvious how climate change affects both humans and environment. The continuous change on weather has a great impact not only to one's physical health but also to the state of our soil, plants, or our agriculture. Although plants

need to be constantly watered and exposed to sunlight, rapid changes may cause problems to the growth of plants.

Climate determines the temperature, weather difference, rainfall totals, and the composition of meteorological phenomena such as the harshness of storms. The reason why we are facing rising temperature, more frequent weather extremes, and natural disasters is because of climate change.

According to Zandalinas et al. (2018), agriculture is calculated to be the most negatively affected by climate change. These climatic problems harshly distress plant progress, yield, and produce massive responses. With sudden differences in environmental conditions, the severe effects on plant productivity are progressing intensely.

One factor of climate change is that it has significant impacts on plant growth. Changes in temperature, atmospheric gases, and carbon dioxide levels can harm microbes, plants, animals, and humans. Additionally, climate change can alter the physiological state of plants, affecting their overall growth. Plants have methods to survive stress which help them combat disadvantageous conditions. Changes in climate metrics, including temperature and climate variability are correlated with the changes in plant rejuvenation and growth quality. The fast reaction in plant traits to climate change may not be sufficient for plants to progress with future climate change

Therefore, the purpose of this study is to ascertain the effects of climate change to the growth of plants as perceived by the agricultural teachers, students, and the farmer themselves. According to the review related literature conducted by the researcher, there have been investigations on this subject. However, no research has been carried out specifically at MSU-Sulu Senior High School.

This gap in research led the researchers to carry out their own study, aiming to delve into the effect of climate change on the growth of plants. The researchers believe that this research will help the teachers, students, farmers, and future researchers help the individual to acclimatize to the changes and combat the effects of climate change.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aimed to determine the effect of climate change to the growth of plants. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What do you think are the most significant challenges that plant face due to climate change?
2. Is climate change the sole factor contributing to the reduction in plant quality?
3. How specifically does climate change influence plant development?

4. How are the farmers at the MSU-Sulu College of Agriculture Demo Farm and its other Demo Farm Extensions adapting to the changes in plant growth induced by climate change?
5. What agricultural practices can be implemented to combat the effects of climate change the sole factor contributing to the reduction in plant quality?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study focused on the effect of climate change on the growth of plants, the research was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu, Philippines College of Agriculture, MSU-Sulu College of Agriculture Demo Farm Indanan Extension, Barangay Langtad, Indanan Sulu which is 9km away from Jolo town proper and MSU-Sulu College of Agriculture Demo Farm Maimbung Extension, at Barangy Lawm Maimbung, Maimbung Sulu which is 12.8km away from Jolo town proper.

Mindanao State University-Sulu was formerly known as MSU-Sulu Development and Technical College (SDTC). The public university is located at Capitol Site, Jolo, Sulu. The government established the campus to rehabilitate the educational situation of the province of Sulu in 1974; the current campus site is about 550 meters from Jolo town proper.

Sampling Method

The participants in this study consists of (10) teacher from the College of Agriculture, as well as (4) caretakers from the MSU- SULU College of Agriculture Demo Farm Extensions.

The reason for selecting these participants is because of their direct involvement and experience in the field of agriculture, which is the primary focus of this research. Teachers provide an academic perspective, while the farmers offer a practical viewpoint based on their daily experiences.

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani et al. (2024), Basir et. al. (2024), Sasapan et. al. (2024), Jarak et. al. (2024) and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

In this research, interviews were formulated. To get the appropriate data needed, the researcher used interview questions as the research instrument. This was used to gather data effectively. The respondents were some of the MSU-Sulu College of Agriculture faculties and the caretakers of MSU-Sulu College of Agriculture Demo Farm Extensions.

Thematic Coding and Analysis

Thematic analysis is the technique used to analyze qualitative data, it allowed the researchers to explore and interpret the richness and depth of the data. According to Virginia (2019) it is a method for analyzing, identifying, and reporting patterns within data. These techniques provide a more comprehensive understanding regarding the research topic.

Data Gathering Procedure

After validating the interview guided question, the researchers secured a written permit to the school director, Dr. Norman A. Abdurahman, and to the dean of College of Agriculture, Prof. Merhama M. Sammah to conduct the study.

The interviews were done and the data has been retrieved, the researchers transposed the collected data into its corresponding range and scale and categorized it. The researchers evaluated the data gathered from the interview and analyzed the said data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data that are gathered from the participants of this study are coded, analyzed, and categorized into themes in this section to further delve into the effects of climate change to the growth of plants.

3.1 Significant challenges that plant face due to climate change

Climate change determines the temperature, weather difference, rainfall totals, and the nature of meteorological phenomena such as the severity of storms. Significantly, these factors affect crop yield and production. Too much of rain or extreme storms may erode and wash away nutrients in the soil. Moreover, Kopeć, (2024) has stated that extreme weather events, such as droughts, floods, heat waves, and cold snaps, pose threats to crops. The high yield and quality in most cultivated plants depend on the quality of the soil. Additionally, Hatfield et al. (2017) extreme temperature and precipitation can prevent crops from growing. Extreme events, especially floods and droughts, can harm crops and reduce yields.

If the weather is too hot, the plant will either die or wilt. (C1, Excerpt 1)

The fruit of the plant may fall, and it will mature early. (C4, Excerpt 2)

Of course, in hot weather, there's a tendency the plant will wither or the leaves

might get burned. (T2, Excerpt 3)

Sunlight is crucial for plant growth and photosynthesis; excessive heat can have negative effects. Plants exposed to extreme heat can experience wilting, similar to sunburn in humans, leading to withering and eventual death. (T6, Excerpt 4)

In too much heat, there are effects to the plants in which cases the leaves will lighten in color and it can also injure the plant. (T3, Excerpt 5)

Based on the participants' narratives, plants when exposed to extreme heat would lead to wilting or death. Although plants need to be exposed to sunlight and is crucial for plant development, exposure to too much heat has negative effects. According to Cho (2022) Extreme precipitation events can disturb plant growth. Additionally, Hatfield et al., (2017) stated that with extreme temperature, drought, prevents crops from growing. Moreover, Ozdemir (2022) stated that even if sunlight is needed for plants to grow, eventually it will destroy the plants in the long run.

It will die if given too much water, and it won't grow well in too much heat. (C1, Excerpt 6)

With natural disasters like flood, the plants may not catch any nutrients and there is a tendency it will rot. (C4, Excerpt 7)

It can affect not just the plants but also its fruits. When there is flood, there is a possibility of soil erosion. Plant growth depends on the climate. (T2, Excerpt 8)

Rain or precipitation is vital for providing water to plants, as water acts as a universal solvent. Excessive water can flood the area, leading to erosion, particularly in the top layer of fertile soil. The presence of organic matter, known as humus, in the water can aid in plant growth and development. Nevertheless, if the rainfall is too heavy and causes flooding and erosion, it can have detrimental effects and damage the plants. (T6, Excerpt 9)

In flood, plants are highly affected; too much water can destroy the plant since there is a limit in how plants absorb water. With climate change, plants won't grow normally especially now, pollution is the one that caused it. Air pollution made by vehicles can produce harmful toxic gases like nitrogen oxide and ethylene. If it is exposed to these gases, it can be poisoned. (T3, Excerpt 10)

Additionally, even water is also a need of plants; too much of it would have negative effects. In natural occurrences like heavy rain and flood, the soil of the plants would be affected; it may remove the topsoil, leading to the soil being unable to hold the nutrients the plants have. It may be washed out or eroded, hence, soil erosion occurs. Moreover, Cho (2022) stated that extreme precipitation events can disturb plant growth. particularly in recently burned forest and make more vulnerable to flooding and soil to erosion. Then, Lawson et al., (2019) said that heavy rain or flooding may disrupt or alter how the plants develop and grow, disrupting pollination. To add up, Balasubramanian (2017) states that soil that is detached by accelerated water or wind erosion maybe transported considerable distances, since soil erosion is one of the issues and challenges that plants face whenever there is rain or flooding.

Climate change disrupts normal plant growth, leading to abnormal patterns and

reduced yields. (T1, Excerpt 11)

It may still grow but it won't bear yields. (C2, Excerpt 12)

It won't grow normally when it is affected by climate change because a factor that causes climate change is air pollution. Air pollution from vehicles produces harmful toxic gases like nitrogen oxide and ethylene. If the plants inhaled large amounts of those toxic gases, it would poison them that result to dying. (T3, Excerpt 13)

Climate change can have a profound effect on plant growth, particularly through abiotic factors like excessive rainfall, high levels of precipitation, or intense sunlight. These factors can significantly influence the growth and development of plants. (T6, Excerpt 14)

Moreover, climate change can indeed affect the normal growth of plants. Changing in temperature or increase in carbon dioxide has a great impact on plants growth hence it won't grow like how it used to be. This leads to abnormal development, decrease yields, and even plant death. Stated by Cho (2022) elevated levels of CO₂ from climate change may enable plants to benefit from the carbon fertilization effect and use less water to grow, but it's not all good news for plants. It's more complicated than that, because climate change is also impacting other factors critical to plants' growth, such as nutrients, temperature, and water. As stated by Rhaman (2021), climate change will alter plant development in ways that will have significant impacts on the function of crop plants and plants in natural ecosystems. Additionally, Gray (2016) Climate change will alter plant development in ways that will have significant impacts on the function of crop plants and plants in natural ecosystems. Future growing conditions will bring increased temperature, increased frequency of extreme events including heatwaves and drought events, and changes in the composition of the atmosphere.

3.2 Climate change as the sole factor of reduction for the quality of plants

Not only climate change could ruin the plants growth, it could also be how the farmers take care of the plants, the way they water the plants, and the type of soil they use. Plants have different types of soil that is suited for them. It's not just climate change. (T4, Excerpt 16)

Actually, climate change can ruin the plants. But sometimes animals can also ruin our plants especially stray animals. (T5, Excerpt 17)

No, actually there are many factors and one of those is climate change. Other factor is the pests. Pests ruin our plants, animals and humans could also ruin the plants. As long as it has the ability to ruin the plants, they are already considered as pests. (T2, Excerpt 18)

Presence of pests can ruin plants. Number 1 causes that damage to growing some plants especially to crops are pests. There are other factors like bacteria, molds, viruses that ruin plants growth and diseases which are caused by animals. It doesn't only focus on climate change; there are many possibilities that contribute to plant quality reduction. (T3, Excerpt 19)

In addition to abiotic factors, biotic factors such as harmful microorganisms and plant pathogens can also affect and damage crops. Living organisms like harmful bacteria, insect pests, and weeds can have a detrimental effect on the growth and

development of plants. (T6, Excerpt 20)

Based on our participants' responses, climate change is not the sole factor contributing to plant quality reduction. Other factors are the presence of pests, stray animals, the suitability of soil, and humans. The participants believe that there are many factors that could ruin the quality of the plants and one of those is climate change. According to Raza et al. (2019) the land and its agriculture are being affected in different ways; variations in annual rainfall, average temperature, heat waves, modifications in weeds, pests or microbes, global change of atmospheric CO₂ or ozone level, and fluctuations in sea level. Research from Saliu et al. (2023) stated that sustainable agricultural practices, including crop rotation, cover cropping, conservation tillage, and organic farming, are instrumental in enhancing soil health and increasing crop yields.

You will notice the changes in leaves, and it doesn't grow well. (C1, Excerpt 21)

You will observe the yields mature early, it will wilt and changed in color. (C4, Excerpt 22)

Too much heat and too much coldness could affect the quality of plants that results to decrease in yields, it will produce less yields due to climate change. If the crops are too exposed to heat, it will burn. Although plants need light or heat to grow, sometimes if it is too much, it will harm them. (T3, Excerpt 23)

Climate change affects the quality of plants especially fruit trees. If a fruit trees normally bear fruit in sunny weather however it suddenly rain, then the fruit which is normally sweet will get bitter because it absorbs the water from the rain. (T5, Excerpt 24)

Too much sunlight or extremely hot weather, such as the current conditions with a heat index of 42°C, often referred to as El Niño, negatively affects plants. It causes soil water to evaporate, preventing plants from absorbing it. (T7, Excerpt 25)

According to the responses of our participants, there are so many ways that they observed how climate change negatively affects the quality of plants. The change of color in plant leaves as well as its crops results in decreasing of yields. If the leaves turn yellowish, it is a sign that the plant is affected by climate change. Ostrowsky et al. (2019) stated that if leaves absorb light, they trap that heat. When leaves reflect light, the heat is reflected in the sky as well. This process controls so much heat that leaf reflectance is a large driving factor in the global climate. Stated by Cho (2022) An elevation in temperature accelerates the lifecycle of plants, resulting in faster maturation. This reduced duration for photosynthesis leads to a decline in grain production and diminished yields.

No, because even if you could revive it, if the plant is not taken care of, it would still rot. (C3, Excerpt 26)

We should have soil conservation. We should keep track on when the plants can be watered and be aware of the soil's water content because of extreme heat, it has a massive effect to the plants. If the plant will get burned, to revive the plant, the soil's moisture level should be high, in order for the plants to be revived. (T3, Excerpt 27)

Take care of the plants and we should always eliminate weeds. Weeds are the great competitor of crop in terms of absorbing nutrients in terms of water and agricultural practices can be used to be able to change and the growth would be good despite climate

change. (T4, Excerpt 28)

One of the factors to the climate change is the uses of synthetic fertilizer, some of the farmers using the chemical to have a big income they don't even care the affected by the nutrition of this chemical there any ways can minimize it by minimal use if synthetic in a way of alternative by using the organic fertilizers. (T9, Excerpt 29)

Yes, we can change back the quality of plants thru proper management. There will always a way like application of organic fertilizer. (T10, Excerpt 30)

There is a way to change or revive the quality of the plants and the participants' responses all connect to proper management. With proper techniques; the usage of organic fertilizers, continuous watering of the plants, elimination of weeds and decayed plants. Despite the effects of climate change, the quality of the plants could be revived or changed back. Moreover, Zheng et al. (2024) stated the potential of organic fertilization in restoring polluted soils and maintaining soil health by suppressing the lability of heavy metals and providing nutrients. The importance of organic fertilization in improving soil quality and ecosystem functioning. Also, Hellin (2023) stated that Synthetic fertilizers are a type of fertilizer designed to supplement natural soil fertility by providing essential nutrients to plants and crops. They are a key component for increasing yields and improving crop quality. Hence, we must eliminate weeds for the betterment of the plants.

3.3 Influence of climate change to the development of plants

Water plants in the morning or evening to avoid heat damage. (T1, Excerpt 31)

If it's extremely hot there is a high tendency that the leaves of the plant would be burned, the respiration of the plants would be high which is damaging to the plants. If there is heavy rain, the plants would be flooded; both should be exact or balanced. (T2, Excerpt 32)

It depends, because there are cases that if it's so hot but the water quantity and fertilizer quality is maintained, the growth would be continuous, as long as it is taken care of well. (T3, Excerpt 33)

Climate change has a significant effect on the growth and development of plants, particularly during crucial stages such as flower formation and fruit production. Without flowers, there will be no fruits. Therefore, climate change adversely affects the plants' ability to produce fruits due to its negative effects. (T6, Excerpt 34)

Climate change can slow down plant growth and development by altering crucial environmental conditions. (T8, Excerpt 35)

In conclusion, the impact of climate change on plant growth and development, particularly during critical stages like flower formation and fruit production, underscores the importance of implementing effective watering practices and proper management of agricultural inputs. Addressing these challenges requires proactive mitigation strategies and adaptive measures to sustainably manage agricultural systems and ensure food security amidst changing environmental conditions. According Cho (2022) Climate change will bring more frequent and severe extreme weather events, including extreme precipitation, wind disturbance, heat waves, and drought. Extreme precipitation events can disturb plant growth, particularly in recently burned forests, and make plants more vulnerable to flooding and soils to erosion. More frequent high winds can stress tree

stands. Narayan Lal et al., (2022) also said that higher temperature promotes sun burn and fruit cracking in many fruit crops and cause serious economic losses. Lastly, Fahad et al., (2021) stated that climatic changes influence all agriculture factors, which can potentially adversely affect their productivity. Plant activities are intimately associated with climate and concentration of atmospheric carbon dioxide which greatly influence plant development.

Usually, the plants' growth and development would not be good. It would weaken and the leaves would not grow bigger. (T4, Excerpt 36)

Climate change has a detrimental effect on plant reproduction, as it leads to increased heat and humidity levels. This can be observed during dry and hot nights, where the weather feels arid despite the presence of air. This condition, known as relative humidity, significantly affects the reproductive processes of plants. (T6, Excerpt 37)

Because of migration the reproduction is affected by the climate change. During the hot season they have many pests, so we are now using chemical to counter it. (T9, Excerpt 38)

Yes, there are many signs how climate change affected the productivity of plants like for example fruits of fruit tree or the harvest will also be low. (T10, Excerpt 39)

We can see how climate change slows down the productivity of the plants, because climate change could rapidly change its weather, either sunny or rainy. If it's sunny, it is possible that it won't grow normally. (T5, Excerpt 40)

There are various signs that they observe about the effects of climate change to the growth of plants. Most of the participants said that climate change will affect the productivity of plants and low harvesting of fruits. Hence, climate change indeed affects the productivity of the plants from the way they grow to their physical aspects that leads to less quality yields to harvest. Raza et al. (2019) said by climate change and food insecurity are the two major issues of the 21st century. Agricultural yield is considerably affected by the adverse weather. With the increase in temperature, the production of major crops has been reduced. While Juroszek et al., (2020) has stated that one of the major concerns with potential climate change is that the frequency of extreme weather events may increase, including cold and heat waves, droughts, heavy precipitation, flooding and storms. These extreme weather events may also affect plant pathogens and related crop disease risks. El-Saadony et al., (2022) also added that plant diseases and pests are risk factors that threaten global food security.

Planting depends on crop adaptation; some prefer moderate climates (T1, Excerpt 41)

Climate change can affect flowering and fruiting patterns by altering sunlight availability, crucial for photosynthesis (T8, Excerpt 42)

Climate change poses challenges right from the beginning of the plant's life cycle, starting with the need for fertile soil when sowing seeds. However, the changing climate has disrupted the traditional rainy season, leading to more frequent droughts and excessive sunlight. This has resulted in a scarcity of water, particularly in the Indanan extension, causing damage to crops in terms of growth, development, and fruit production. The lack of water and excessive heat often lead to seeds germinating but

failing to produce fruits, highlighting the absence of development despite growth. (T6, Excerpt 43)

It still depends, smoke can induce flowering. Ethylene is an essential plant hormone. Especially, the plant hormone ethylene can bear. (T3, Excerpt 44)

The ability of plants to produce flowers varies, with some not flowering at all and others known for their flowering capabilities. Climate change can influence the fruiting and flowering patterns of plants. (T7, Excerpt 45)

Based on the participants' responses, it can be concluded that climate change has a significant impact on the flowering and fruiting patterns of plants. The changing climate, including factors like sunlight availability and water scarcity, can disrupt the growth, development, and fruit production of crops. Additionally, the ability of plants to produce flowers can vary, and smoke and ethylene are factors that can induce flowering. Additionally, Rajatiya (2018), said that the changing of climatic parameters disturbs the flowering pattern. A change in field-level climate may alter the need and timing of irrigation. It affects the crop physiology, biochemistry, floral biology, biotic stresses like disease-pest incidence that results to the reduction of yield and quality of fruit crops. To add up, Isoda et al., (2021) stated plant hormones play important roles in plant growth and development and physiology, and in acclimation to environmental changes.

3.4 Farmers adapting to the changes of plants due to climate change

Of course, when the plants are accustomed to the rainy season then sunny season comes, you should really water the plants because once you neglect the plants, and there is a huge tendency that they will die. (C1, Excerpt 46)

If it is sunny season, we water the plants daily, morning and afternoon. (C2, Excerpt 47)

If it is rainy season, we minimize watering the plants. (C3, Excerpt 48)

We adjust to changes in plant growth through fertilizer management. (C4, Excerpt 49)

These responses show that there is more than one way to adjust to the changes in plants' growth caused by climate change one of it is watering the plants daily when the climate is too hot. It may be challenging for them as a caretaker, they still manage to adjust by keen observation and swift adaptation to the shifting of weather patterns. Hence, being flexible and responsive to the needs of plants regardless of climate change is the best way to ensure their survival and growth. Stated by Malhi et al. (2021) The usage of traditional management systems and agroecological management systems, namely biodiversification, soil management, and water harvesting, can help farmers adopt climate-resilient technologies. Co (2019) said the use of pesticides and chemicals can harm plant health and contribute to climate change by releasing harmful substances into the environment. By avoiding these substances, we can help support plant survival and reduce the negative impacts on the environment. As well as, Jin (2019) stated that agriculture is a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions, particularly methane and nitrous oxide. Improving farming practices, such as reducing tillage, incorporating cover crops, and reducing synthetic fertilizer use, can help reduce these emissions. Additionally,

reducing meat and dairy consumption or adopting a vegan diet can help reduce the demand for animal products and reduce the environmental impacts of agriculture. Moreover, Jazeera (2019) said planting trees is a simple and effective way to reduce carbon emissions, combat climate change, and promote sustainable land use practices. By supporting reforestation efforts and planting trees in our own communities, we can help to create a healthier planet for future generations.

It actually depends on the plants, especially in fruit trees you should take care of it well. One example is the patchay plant; you should remove some parts that are rotten in order for it to not contaminate the other plants. (C1, Excerpt 50)

We have planting techniques, the plant should have at least 5 leaves then we could plant it. (C2, Excerpt 51)

Yes, after we plant it, we put plastic on so that if it has fertilizer, the nutrients would go directly to the bottom and to the roots so that it will grow. (C3, Excerpt 52)

We observe the plant, because sometimes the leaves turn yellow it means it is low in nutrients, so we put cow manure then we water the plants. Then after 3 days, you can already see it changing. (C4, Excerpt 53)

In our participants' responses, it can be seen that the techniques used by the farmers are through observing the plant state, what plant it is, removing the rotten parts and then using organic fertilizers. The farmers suggest that we use organic fertilizers rather than chemical fertilizers, for it is not good for the plant it is also a factor contributing to climate change. According to Zhou et al. (2022) Organic fertilization practices can improve crop yields and soil quality. Moreover, Lemery (2023) stated that adopting practices associated with organic and regenerative agriculture, such as cover crops, pesticide use reduction, rotational grazing, and composting, can help nurture the soil and reduce emissions from nitrogen-based fertilizers. Additionally, according to Datta (2023), farmers can utilize climate forecasting tools, plant cover crops, and adopt other strategies to manage climate-related production threats. While Swenson (2022) apply fertilizers, prevent animals from entering streams, and take actions to minimize nutrient-laden runoff.

In my perspective, regarding of using fertilizer, there is such thing we called steps in planting crops. There must be a distance that must be followed; the crops must be arranged when planted. (C1, Excerpt 54)

We taught them the effects of climate change as well as the signs of climate change and also the signs that the crops are not growing well, in that situation, we advised them to use organic fertilizer like Vermi Cas. (C2, Excerpt 55)

They should plant the crops in a good way in order for them to avoid any damages to plants and for it to grow well. (C3, Excerpt 56)

We will check if there are any wilted plants so we can take action immediately. We will apply fertilizers such as Vermi Cas and Cow Manure for them to help themselves. (C4, Excerpt 57)

Based on the caretakers' statements they collectively emphasize the significance of adapting careful management practices in agriculture, especially amidst the challenges posed by climate change. They stress the necessity of careful fertilizer application,

recognition of climate change symptoms, utilization of organic fertilizers such as Vermi Cas, observing appropriate planting techniques, and quick intervention to address crop distress. Overall, their insights advocate for an approach to crop refinement aimed to nourish plant growth and productivity while effectively ease the adverse effects of climate change. Moreover, Czembor (2022) there are agricultural practices that involve changing planting dates. One such practice is the adaptive management of crop growing periods by adjusting sowing dates, as mentioned in a study on global crop yields. Czembor (2019) said that modifying planting dates in agriculture can help farmers maximize yields, improve crop health, and better cope with the impacts of climate change. Czembor (2020) proves in his research that farmers determine the optimal planting date for their crops based on factors like soil temperature, moisture, and expected weather conditions. The planting date is crucial as it influences crop development and yield potential. In practice, farmers consider soil temperature, aiming to plant once it has risen above a certain threshold, typically around 50°F, and is expected to continue to rise.

3.5 Agricultural practices to fight the climate change

As professional in this field, there are many ways to lessen the cause of climate change. Like for example, in farming, we can lessen the cause of climate change like for not burning the residues, instead of burning the residues, we will decompose it, make it into fertilizer. Minimize the use of chemical fertilizers, because burning those remains will produce methane gas which contributes to air pollution. (T9, Excerpt 58)

As professional practices I teach how the proper way to take care of plants by way of watering to minimize and to have a good growth and development of the plants (T4, Excerpt 59)

As a plant professional, I advise against improper garbage disposal, particularly burning materials like plastic soda bottles. This practice can harm the ozone layer and have a detrimental impact on the environment, leading to increased heat. (T7, Excerpt 60)

As a licensed agriculturist, we can provide assistance to the youth, students, stakeholders, and farmers in addressing climate change. There is an importance of patience and that climate change is a result of God's will. However, I also acknowledge the scientific understanding of environmental factors contributing to climate change. I encourage my students to have faith in God, be patient, and view climate change as a reminder to pray. (T6, Excerpt 61)

As a professional in the field of plants, the normal practice: which is planting more trees, plant more on organic. Like now they waste large quantities of fertilizers. But now the latest technology of agriculture, they have precision agriculture. Precision agriculture prevents the waste of the input which is the fertilizer, water and pesticides. A small amount is applied, but it can save more input. Excessive use and waste of inputs contribute to climate change for it causes land, air, and water pollution. So, we apply the actual practice, which is the precision agriculture; precise amount only needed to apply the inputs. (T3, Excerpt 62)

The following participants are licensed agriculturists or professional in field of agriculture, as they teach students about plants, they also preach the effects of climate

change as it is evident and affecting the plants growth. It includes in planting more trees, how to take care of the plants since it contributes to the lessening of the effects of climate change, not burning some residues, practicing proper garbage disposal, and proper use of agricultural input. As stated by Volk et al. (2023) Plants play a critical role in the global carbon cycle and are key to climate change mitigation and adaptation solutions. Through photosynthesis, plants remove carbon dioxide (CO₂) from the atmosphere and store it as plant biomass. Moreover, stated by Khan et al., (2023) the impacts of ecological stresses on plant growth and the mitigation of these impacts using plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR). The threats to plants due to the increase in global population and desertification, which further accelerate the negative impacts of climate change on plant growth and food supply. To add up, Choudhary et al.,(2022) said that the impact of climate change on the plant holobiont and developing mitigation strategies for sustainable agriculture. Understanding the effects of climate change on the plant holobiont at the agroecosystem level and implementing holistic mitigation strategies.

Adapt by selecting suitable crops each season and managing water effectively. (T1, Excerpt 63)

When it rains heavily, we need to prevent soil erosion that can damage our crops and nutrients. Is it necessary for us to plant copper crosses. These act as barriers to prevent excessive erosion of our plants. (T2, Excerpt 64)

Usually, we are undergoing process to eliminate trades so water the plants as much as possible so we will use organic fertilizers. (T4, Excerpt 65)

Tree planting is an agricultural practice that can contribute to regulating the temperature of our environment. Plants have the ability to stabilize temperatures, making it beneficial to plant more trees. (T7, Excerpt 66)

Agricultural practices promoting carbon sequestration can combat climate change impacts. (T8, Excerpt 67)

Based on the responses provided, adapting to climate change in agriculture involves selecting suitable crops, managing water effectively, preventing soil erosion, using organic fertilizers, planting trees for temperature regulation, and promoting carbon sequestration. These practices are crucial in mitigating the impacts of climate change on agriculture and ensuring sustainable farming. According to Grigorieva et al. (2023) use of different crops or crop varieties, and plant breeding or development of new crop varieties more suitable to the changing climate—higher temperatures and/or reduced precipitation and hence, water availability. In accordance to Belmin et al. (2023) climate change adaptation options that focus on transforming production systems, providing access to knowledge useful for climate change adaptation in agriculture, and coordinating and financing adaptation actions at territorial or sector scale. Then, stated by McCarthy et al. (2022) farmers are implementing various adaptation measures for agriculture, including the use of drought-resistant crops, shifting rain patterns, and investing in climate adaptation measures to tackle climate change challenges.

In plants, in planting date, there is this required month depends on whether if it is hot or cold but now, climate change changes yearly that there are times sunny season comes first than rainy season or vice versa and that affects the planting dates. (T2,

Excerpt 68)

Plants have their own season, especially those big crops like fruit trees, it is by season, and its date cannot be adjusted. We can still plant them anytime however it is hard for them to bear fruit because it has its exact time to produce. In some cases, perennial trees bear fruit once they reach a certain required height. Depending on its soil nutrition, macronutrients like hydrogen, oxygen, carbon, phosphorus, potassium and so on and so forth. If there is no lack of nutrients in the soil, you can still plant anytime. But when it comes to producing yields, it may take time because it has its fruiting season. (T3, Excerpt 69)

In terms of planting dates, yes because we will be looking forward to the climate. In every crop, they have their own different season, so if suited to the climate maybe is the time to plant the crops. (T4, Excerpt 70)

Agricultural practices can be adapted by adjusting planting dates to accommodate changes caused by climate change. Plants are classified as either short-day or long-day plants based on their daylight requirements for growth. However, climate change has disrupted the planting calendar, leading to shifts in the classification of plants. (T6, Excerpt 71)

To mitigate the effects of climate change, adjusting planting dates is a valuable agricultural practice. It is crucial to determine the appropriate seasons or specific dates for planting specific crops or plants. (T7, Excerpt 72)

Adjusting planting dates can help adapt to changing climates and optimize crop growth. (T8, Excerpt 73)

Based on the responses of our participants, it shows that there is changing planting dates to mitigate the effect of climate change. This means closely observing the climate and determining the best time to plant specific crops based on the suitable climate. By being responsive to the effects of climate change, we can optimize crop growth and ensure agricultural productivity regardless of the climate change. According to [Grigorieva et al. \(2023\)](#) One of agricultural adaptation strategies is adjustments in planting dates such as changes in harvest and sowing dates, e.g., later sowings, sowings to suit rainfall variability, etc. Moreover, [Jiang et al. \(2021\)](#) changing planting dates is considered an effective adaptive strategy to mitigate the negative impacts of climate change on crop yields on a global scale, such as in Northeast China. Modelling adaptation strategies to reduce adverse impacts of climate change through adjusting planting dates can enhance crop resilience and productivity in changing climatic conditions.

Conclusions

The significant challenges that plants face when exposed to extreme heat would be wilting or the withering of plants, while in heavy rain or flood, there would be soil erosion whereas the nutrients of the plants would be washed away. The change in weather or increase in carbon dioxide would affect the plant growth, which leads to decreased yields and plant death.

Moreover, even climate change greatly affects plant growth and its quality, there are other factors contributing to it as well. The presence of pests, stray animals, state of

the soil, as well as humans could contribute to the decrease of plant quality. One sign where a plants' quality is affected is by observing its color. If a plant turns yellowish, it is affected by climate change and is not been taken care of. In order to revive or change its quality to its original, healthy state, proper management should be done. Techniques such as continuous watering of plants, removal of decayed parts, and adding organic fertilizers would revive the plant.

Additionally, the effect of climate change to plant growth and development especially during its fruiting stage is very critical. It could result to a low harvest of fruits and low productivity of plants since it affects how plants grow to their physical state. Changing of climate results to sunlight availability and water scarcity, can disrupt the growth, development, and fruit production of crops. Additionally, the ability of plants to produce flowers can vary, and smoke and ethylene are factors that can induce flowering.

As famers are the ones exposed to the actual plantation, it is challenging to adjust to climate change since it is undetermined. However, by keen observation and adaptation to weather patterns, one should still be responsive and flexible to the needs of the plants regardless climate change. In order to heed to plant needs, observing the plant state should be first in order to know what fertilizers and methods are suitable. Careful management and practices are to be observed and usage of organic fertilizers would effectively combat and prevent the effects of climate change.

It is concluded that planting more trees, plants, proper disposal of garbage, not burning plastics and residues, and proper use of agricultural input would lessen climate change and its effect.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this qualitative study on climate change and its effect to the growth of plants, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To the caretakers: Organic Fertilizer. The researchers recommend the usage of organic fertilizer to the caretakers/farmers rather than chemical fertilizers. Although chemical fertilizers make plants look physically healthy, its taste, development, and taste would differ and could be extremely harmful to one's health and the environment. As there are many factors contributing to plant quality reduction like the presence and effects of pests, organic fertilizers work in reviving plants. With organic fertilizers, plants could grow and absorb natural nutrients. It also helps with the lessening of climate change. Additionally, Singh (2012) stated that organic fertilizer, replenishes the soil, naturally, without leaving chemical residue, and gives the plants a healthier and are safer than chemical fertilizer. This would ideally produce good crop yield with minimal impact on ecological factors. To prove this, Verma et al., (2019) stated that to prevent the ill effects of chemicals to the plants and to the environment, organic fertilizers must be utilized for better soil and environmental management and effects.

2. To the caretakers and teachers. Greenhouse. The researches recommend both caretakers and teachers about greenhouse. Teachers may provide an insight and teach students the benefits of greenhouses to the plants development and its positive impact to the environment and caretakers/farmers could have plenty of harvest and could plant non-heat loving plants or fruits. Building a greenhouse protects the plants from external factors like heavy rain, wind, presence of animals or pests, and air contamination. It provides regulation of temperature and humidity inside, enhancing crop quality and yield. According to Slathia et al. (2018) with the use of greenhouse, the protected cultivation of high value crops has become irreplaceable both from economic and environmental points of view. It offers several advantages to grow high value crops with improved quality even under unfavorable and marginal environments and Zhang et al., (2022) states that greenhouses are crucial for sustainable crop production since it prolongs the production season of various crops by providing controlled indoor microclimate conditions.

3. To the caretakers: Mulching Techniques. Mulching, specifically plastic mulch maintains moisture and regulates temperature of the soil and prevents the growth of weeds. By applying mulching, it improves soil health and avoids erosion. El-Beltagi et al. (2022) stated in his study that plastic mulches can significantly improve soil health and pest management. One of the many benefits of mulching the soil surface is that it reduces soil evaporation or erosion brought on by wind or water. Mulching at a depth of 5 cm is the most often advised method for reducing weed development. Additionally, since soil erosion is one of the problems and a challenge for agriculture, Balasubramanian (2017) recommended practices such as mulching.

4. To the teachers: Organic Agriculture. The researchers recommend teachers organic agriculture to implement and teach agricultural students in order for students to be aware of the dangers and effects of using modern technology as a mode of farming. Since organic agriculture; usage of organic fertilizers, planting more crops and trees, using old crops to make fertilizers are ways to reducing climate change. Moreover, Holka et al. (2022) said that organic farming; an absence of mineral fertilizers eliminates greenhouse gases emissions from the application of fertilizers on the field as well as from fertilizer production. One of the solutions in mitigating climate change is agroforestry. This consists in mixing woody plants with arable, leading agricultural production in a sustainable and environmentally friendly manner. Additionally, Samui et al., (2024) stated that organically managed systems can help to mitigate climate change through careful regulation of soil nutrients, resulting in reduced nitrous oxide emissions from soils.

5. To the future researchers: Proper Management. The researchers recommend that the future researchers must first know how to properly manage and use the given agricultural practices in order for the plants to thrive even in extreme weather extremes. In extreme heat, plants need to be constantly watered to ensure a good amount of soil moisture level to prevent the withering of plants, while in rainy season; barriers or cover crops should be made in order for the plants not to be eroded. Stated by Haruna et al. (2020) one way to reduce soil erosion and manage soil and its nutrients for productivity is through cover crops. Cover crops are grown because of the numerous benefits they

provide, including protecting the soil from wind and water erosion. With the cover crops, the soil moisture or the water content would be conserved even in extreme heat. To add up, Verma et al., (2019) states that even though organic fertilizers are recommended, there are still limitations on how to use these applications and proper management should be addressed and evaluated. Moreover, Balasubramanian (2017) states that in order for a successful and long-term plant life, proper management of agricultural practices must be utilized.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study prioritized participant confidentiality, ensuring data is used solely for research purposes. The research was conducted in accordance with ethical guidelines and regulations. Key data was accessible only to authorized researchers. The study followed ethical principles in its design, implementation, and analysis. Results were analyzed and disseminated to contribute to scientific knowledge and inform future studies.

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